

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BUGRE****FIRST NAME: MAMUDU ZANYA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2023 for MAC)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Writing an Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-11)
2. Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. The Correct Use of Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
4. Using American English vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
6. Style Guides and Using the Turabian Style (EUCLID 2021, 41-57)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1 (EUCLID 2021)

1) INTRODUCTION

This program is my second postgraduate degree, so I am familiar with writing academic essays. However, the last time I wrote an academic paper was two years ago since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. I found it, therefore, very refreshing to study and interact with the ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack for Period One provided by EUCLID as an introductory course to the Program of Doctor of Philosophy [Ph.D.] in International Law and Treaty Law (DILT). It is essential to start with this module since it gives the student the standard expected by EUCLID. Further, different universities have different rules regarding writing academic papers. I will use the terms "Academic Writing" and "Academic Essay" interchangeably in this paper.

This introductory course provides the student with knowledge on the basics of international academic and professional paper writing, including, among other things, good essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, the variances between the usage of American English versus British English, and the rules of styles. Moreover, the course material for

period one “introduces the student to academic writing at Euclid University” (EUCLID 2021, 3). The other materials provided with the initial email from the course structure, such as the Student Orientation Pack, How to Write a Response Paper, and the Sample Response Papers, were very helpful in clarifying the course expectations and highlighting what the student should concentrate on.

I was initially lost in dealing with the volume of material that I had to read or study. Nevertheless, I realized that the documents provided were complementary as I read through them one by one. Now that I have finished the reading for Period One, I am ready to write my first Response Paper. I have chosen to write on the seven key topics covered in all the chapters. Of course, I will focus more on the chapters dealing with Essay Writing, Punctuation, Plagiarism, and Style Guides. For the rest, I will provide the key takeaways that I have learned.

Finally, the study material includes a Vimeo video that is an introduction to formatting documents in Microsoft Word and using the templates provided by EUCLID for response papers. The video introduces the student to formatting documents using the tools provided for paragraph styles, referencing, and citations required by EUCLID, as well as other rules of style. In addition, the use of language, that is, either US English or UK English, is covered.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

What is academic writing, and how is an academic essay different from other types of writing? Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma define an academic essay or scholarly writing as “nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work” (EUCLID 2021, 7). There is an African adage that the success of a man’s journey starts with knowing where he is going before he starts his journey. Therefore, starting with a definition is critical to writing an academic essay.

What is more: “Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions” (EUCLID 2021, 7). The end of any academic writing, such as a doctoral dissertation, is to answer a research question or hypothesis underlying the relevant research. Hence, understanding the topic for the academic essay is crucial in formulating and writing the hypothesis and answering it, which in turn derives from reading, organizing, and writing.

Sometimes, we take certain things like writing academic essays for granted, especially if one has already undertaken postgraduate studies. However, relearning the basics of academic writing was very exciting for me. It brought memories of my university years and how I struggled as a non-native English speaker to learn introduction to academic writing. Going through the basic concepts again refreshed my memory and clarified the logic of good essay writing.

There are certain prescribed steps, albeit flexible in application, to be considered when writing an academic essay. Cleenewerck and Gulma recommend the following: First, even before starting to write the essay, one must adhere to three basic steps: First, “early start-up...have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. *It is never advisable to procrastinate* [italics added]” (EUCLID 2021, 7). As the English poet Edward Young wrote in his 1742 poem, “Procrastination is the thief of time” (Shatz 2023), my experience has taught me to start my essays early. As a mature student having to juggle with little time for family and work, it is always tempting and convenient to procrastinate. I have learned that it is much better to read for 30 minutes a day than to cram at the weekend. Second, “defining the question and analyzing the task...analyzing and presenting answers to the question is key” (EUCLID 2021, 7). Third, “drafting an initial plan” (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Taking the time to write out a plan for the essay is the most important part of writing a good essay. The initial plan will guide not only the structure but also the content of the essay. Having a plan would guide, if not force, the student to think critically and creatively in their research work. As noted by Cleenewerck and Gulma:

Having a plan for going about the essay is very necessary. The plan should include your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic, constituting your preliminary essay plan that will guide your research. If an essay plan is written correctly, it will help you work out how you will answer the question and the type of information to use (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Research is the fulcrum of any good academic paper. “Reading and research will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer (EUCLID 2021, 8). Good research focuses on answering the thesis question by finding the evidence to support it or otherwise. On a personal note, while I find the section of the reading material on researching the topic helpful and given the abundant availability of online research tools and editing tools, such as Zotero, I believe the whole section should be revised to include how to use the internet for research.

To end this section, I now turn to the structure of any academic writing. An academic essay must consist of - 1) an introduction, 2) a main body, and 3) a conclusion. An academic essay must start with an introduction section, where one directs the readers to the thesis question and a summary of the main ideas to be expounded in the paper. The main body consists of the research material as evidence to answer the hypothesis made through argumentation for and against the thesis proposal. The essay must end with the conclusion section. Unlike the introduction, the conclusion begins with a summary of the answer to the thesis question or hypothesis and the key ideas from the evidence provided in the main arguments. The conclusion ends by looking at the future impact of the findings, the implications for future research, and how to use the evidence gathered.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

Cleenewerck and Gulma provide some suggestions to students for writing good academic papers. As it is with everything we do in life, some basic rules or guidelines help

us all achieve a well-balanced life filled with joy and happiness. The rules of thumb for writing academic papers summarize what we discussed in the previous section and common-sense guidelines to help every student write professionally. In addition, a mastery of these seemingly straightforward rules will help avoid unnecessary time wasted in editing and re-editing papers, as well as enable the student to write with clarity and to communicate effectively.

Since the purpose of any academic paper is to answer a thesis question or hypothesis, it is vital at the beginning of the paper to let the reader know what the thesis question or proposal is and how you intend to answer it. Stating the thesis question is imperative that "If you do not have a thesis, get one" (EUCLID 2021, 13). Not having a thesis question for an academic essay can be compared to building a house with a foundation. Academic papers must focus on the subject being discussed by examining the critical questions or issues arising from the thesis of the paper, and an evaluation of the outcomes.

To write effectively, you must be yourself and write in your own style. Be precise and concise in your choice of words. Avoid long sentences and paragraphs, be evidence-based, and always reference your work with the correct citations. Use quotation sparingly unless the quotation buttresses the point you are making. Pay particular attention to every opinion you deem important to include in your paper. I find the advice to "read your paper out loud" (EUCLID 2021,14) intriguing because I always understand what I write better if I read it out loud, or when I say the words out loud as I write.

Of course, I can only conclude talking about rules of thumb for writing academic papers if I emphasize the necessity of referencing one's work and attributing an idea or ideas that are original to the author of that idea or those ideas. I will be dealing with plagiarism later.

4) THE CORRECT USE OF PUNCTUATION

The correct use of punctuation in academic writing is one of the most fundamental issues in essay writing. I have found it very difficult to comprehend journal articles or chapters of papers I have read due to the imprecise punctuation used. The correct use of punctuation marks is noteworthy in our day and age when most of our communication takes place on social media or by email, where shorthand is very often used with no regard for punctuation. I have always struggled to use punctuations correctly, except for the assistance with Microsoft Word spellcheck and autocorrections.

The most challenging punctuation marks for me are the brackets, specifically square brackets. The proper use of the Comma, which is very important to writing in general, can sometimes be confusing to non-native English speakers. In addition, I find the exhaustive explanation of the use of quotation marks beneficial, especially the use of other punctuation with quotations, as this is quite challenging to understand. Having said that, I will adhere to the general rule that "use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16).

5) USING AMERICAN ENGLISH VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

It is not uncommon to read a report at my workplace where the spellings of American and British English are used together in the same report. As a person who grew up in a British colony, we have often used the 'Queen's language' as the standard against all other English, including American English. However, as I started to travel and work in an international environment, I realized that the most predominant form of English spoken and written is American English.

I have never paid much attention to the differences between American English and British English until this course. It has been a fascinating discovery. I only thought the difference was made up of spellings, but I discovered there were more. For instance, I did not know that certain words or phrases had different meanings in both languages. Moreover, I learned that the use of periods, commas, and quotation marks differs when used in American English. For example, while there is a full stop (period) at the end of the abbreviation Mr. in American English, it is omitted in British English.

At the start of the course, I did not understand why EUCLID placed such importance on using either American English or UK English to write papers and to be consistent in the use of the language selected. Although most international readers will not make the difference, I do understand why it will be a good practice to use either American English or British English in writing papers.

6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is central to writing academic papers. Cleenewerck and Gulma define plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). Plagiarism is about doing what is right and ethical. After all, academic papers are all about using existing theories or ideas to argue and defend one’s thesis and to contribute to knowledge on a particular subject. Therefore, using another person’s ideas without acknowledging the author is theft, period!

The good news is that everyone can avoid plagiarism. One can do this by giving credit or acknowledging the source of information through a citation in the paper. Although one would always endeavor to avoid plagiarizing other people’s work, it is impossible to be original at all times. There are instances where one can use the original idea and express it in one's own words (paraphrasing). As a general rule, one does not have to cite a source “when the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas” (EUCLID 2021, 37).

7) STYLE GUIDES AND USING THE TURABIAN STYLE

Understanding the rules of style is critical to being a student of EUCLID because the use of writing style is a cardinal issue in academic writing. EUCLID recommends the

use of the Chicago Rules (Turabian style) for formatting papers and assignments, although other styles of writing are permitted. A style guide is a “means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41). Writing styles delimit different aspects of writing, among other things, like spelling s, readership consideration, use of abbreviations, choice of language, sentence, and paragraph structure.

During my undergraduate studies at an American Theological Seminary, I used *Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996*, as a guide for writing my term papers and my thesis. Consequently, I am already familiar with the rules. Nevertheless, it was refreshing to study the material.

8) CONCLUSION

I have been looking forward to another academic challenge, and I am excited to enroll in this doctoral program. I am motivated and anxious at the same time to be a student again. It has been a refreshing experience to read through the orientation material, the course pack for ACA-401/ACA-401D, as well as the accompanying videos on LMS.

The introductory material at first sounded repetitive, but after going through the readings, I can understand the rationale behind getting the student familiar with the EUCLID and what is expected of him or her. As noted earlier, the course material for period one would require another revision to include tools for internet research. The provision of the Premium version of Grammarly is well thought out by the faculty of EUCLID, as it will be valuable for the student throughout the program of study.

REFERENCES

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